

Knowledge Graphs and interoperability techniques for hybrid-cloud deployment of FaaS applications

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Abstract—Towards enabling the automated and optimized FaaS deployment of applications in a hybrid-cloud setting, the application requirements should be met by comparing them to the capabilities of the available resources of available clusters. To this end, semantic matching between the application characteristics and the individual descriptions of available compute clusters (e.g. from public or private cloud or edge facilities available) is required. In this work, such a system is proposed, namely the Reasoning Framework, which performs semantic matching between application and resource (meta)data and facilitates information sharing among the FaaS platform components leveraging Knowledge Graphs, ontology technologies, and semantic reasoning. The proposed system harvests information from the application function workflow, provided as a graph by the function editor specification (based on Node-RED), including developer-inserted annotations during the design process, and maps them to the dynamic information retrieved from the available clusters. The Reasoning Framework interprets these data as graphs and automatically applies several semantic rules that enable filtering of the available resources and efficient information retrieval through a RESTfull interface. The paper also discusses experimental results to further showcase the advantages of the proposed approach.

Index Terms—semantic matching, reasoning, knowledge graph, knowledge engineering, inference, FaaS

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I. INTRODUCTION

Function as a service (FaaS) is a novel cloud computing service that provides a platform allowing customers to develop, run, and manage application functionalities without the complexity of building and maintaining the infrastructure typically associated with developing and launching an app [1]. In such a setting, applications could be perceived as function workflows consisting of linked functions, services or actions that potentially have different requirements in terms of computational resources, latency and performance [2].

Furthermore, depending on the use case, some functions or services should be hosted at the edge, while others at public or private available resource clusters. Moreover, aspects such as locality, latency and type of the target infrastructure should be considered for efficient deployment of a given application since some functions may be invoked from a specific region or require for example a GPU-enabled node [3]. For instance, in the agriculture sector, IoT-based applications leverage data from sensors placed in multiple greenhouses to train machine learning or simulation models for optimizing plant management and yield. In such cases, deploying some functions of the workflow may be subject to functional limitations. For example, data collection can not reside anywhere else but the node inside the greenhouse, in order to communicate with the sensors. On the other hand, simulation models are typically too heavyweight for edge resources to accommodate, thus needing

more large scale cloud resources. Finally, specific tasks (e.g. preprocessing) could be performed in either location, depending on an optimized decision process (e.g. data preprocessing near the edge in order to avoid costly data transfers).

Enabling a workflow to be deployed to different clouds or even on sensors at the edge of the cloud still has to overcome many challenges, including the matchmaking between functions and available resources considering customer-specific requirements [4], interoperability issues among functions in a workflow [5] and lack of standardization between different cloud environments. The latter results in vendor lock-in and limited transferability from platform to platform or from cloud provider to cloud provider [2].

This work proposes a service that relies on knowledge graphs, custom semantics and interoperability techniques allowing for the automated and optimized deployment of FaaS applications in hybrid cloud environments. In essence the main contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- Proposal of a novel architecture that fits between application design time and infrastructure descriptions. The approach allows for the hybrid deployment of FaaS applications by abstracting the individual specifications and characteristics of the input applications and computer clusters and facilitating information retrieval needed in FaaS applications' development and hosting.
- Presentation of a real-world implementation of this architecture along with its derived benefits.

In the remainder of this paper, Section II maps related work on this topic, while section III describes the context of the broader methodological approach. Section IV presents the internal architecture as well as implementation details of the proposed mechanism. Section V demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed mechanism and finally, section VI summarises the paper and provides recommendations on future research avenues.

II. RELATED WORK

The most prominent FaaS offerings are provided by the major cloud service providers (CSPs) such as Amazon AWS Lambda, IBM, Google, and Azure Cloud Functions that probably employing state-of-the-art techniques for functions deployment. Nevertheless, their proprietary nature limits the understanding of system internals while hybrid cloud deployment is out of their scope.

Reflecting to this limitation, other stakeholders present different types of architectures for deploying serverless workflows in multi or hybrid clouds relying on open-source FaaS frameworks (i.e., Apache OpenWhisk, OpenFaaS, Kubeless and Fisson). For example, the SPEC Cloud Group [6] focuses on this topic and proposes a reference architecture for FaaS applications stating that the platform should include a metadata store for low-latency look-ups of function metadata. Authors in [4] suggest the use of semantics in order to perceive the application workflow and resources as graphs enabling exploitation and combination of the two sources of semantics. In [3] the authors present a container scheduling system

that enables existing serverless frameworks to support edge functions and better use edge resources that leverage metadata to communicate information about functions and compute nodes to the scheduler. In this research, the authors focus on the design of the system, rather than its implementation.

Fogbow [7] focuses on provisioning virtual machines in a heterogeneous multi-cloud setting, where the workflows will be deployed [8], offering limited and not standardized interoperability between AWS and Azure clusters. Although the system presented in [9] enables multi-cloud deployments of FaaS applications to optimize execution time, function placement among different IaaS providers is not available. Authors in [10] present an architecture for deploying a serverless application in multiple CSPs without considering edge or private clouds. Besides, the paper does not elaborate on the implementation details of the module responsible for filtering the available cloud resources.

Various works rely on OASIS TOSCA language to map application requirements and cloud resources specifications semantically. Notably, authors in [11] propose an extension in TOSCA for supporting edge and fog deployments that could facilitate FaaS-based applications. However, TOSCA-based approaches capture only the application requirements without considering additional information such as function code and sequences of workflow tasks for performing applications and resource matchmaking. Moreover, TOSCA does not enable the conceptualization of such information as graphs.

Since serverless systems abstract the infrastructure details from the user, these systems should automatically understand applications' requirements and workload characteristics for an optimized deployment. Leveraging semantic reasoning, knowledge graphs and semantics could facilitate diverse workload management [12], which is still an issue in the FaaS platforms [13]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, implementing a service utilizing semantics in the form of knowledge graphs to accommodate hybrid cloud deployment of FaaS applications is still an open challenge [1]. At the same time, related works are limited to the inclusion of semantics and interoperability in conceptual reference architectures.

III. SERVERLESS PLATFORM OVERVIEW

The presented service is part of a platform being developed in the H2020 PHYSICS project¹ which aims at enabling the optimized deployment of FaaS application in hybrid cloud environments while abstracting the infrastructure layer for the customer. Fig. 1 illustrates the positioning of the proposed service, the Reasoning Framework (RF), with relation to other platform components.

Specifically, the developer designs its application in a Node-RED based design environment (DE) which supports the inclusion of annotations both at flow and function level [14]. These annotations may be provided by the developer or by the platform itself. The output of the developed workflows is serialized in JSON format and transformed in a formal

¹<https://physics-faas.eu/>

Fig. 1. Reasoning Framework's dependencies with other components.

application description schema that is based on Web Ontology Language (OWL) [15]. OWL serves as a common vocabulary interpreting the whole application as a graph. The latter is then injected to the RF in JSON-LD format. The underlying data include all the information required for the application's deployment in a FaaS setting, such as the flows' executable docker image location, execution mode (function or service), and various annotations (e.g., locality, memory size, preference on energy/performance etc., specific hardware needs etc.) populated by the developer, that need to be in line with the target infrastructure capabilities (see Fig. 2).

Likewise, descriptions from the available clusters, which are using Kubernetes² as the resource manager, are obtained from a service installed in each cluster. This service, translates the cluster description in a unified format according to an ontology presented in [16] and is available in GitHub³. The created triples from each available cluster are ingested (also in JSON-LD format) to the RF forming the resource graph. The structure of sample resource data ingested in the RF from an Elastic Kubernetes Cluster (EKS) is illustrated in Fig 3. This data includes information regarding the cluster locality, sizing (i.e., CPU, RAM), architecture, each cluster node's operating system, and metrics related to the performance, energy consumption, and resilience.

RF facilitates the semantic matching between application requirements and resource capabilities to alleviate functions' placement in the optimal cluster. It is noted that the RF acts as a first level filter of the resources while the optimization task performs in the next platform component. In addition, RF provides various types of information to other components based on their requirements such as OpenWhisk⁴ manifest files.

IV. REASONING FRAMEWORK

Semantic reasoning is required to infer relationships and automatically match data stemming from different contexts (i.e., application workflows and code, and infrastructure). The most prominent solution to present structural relations between the entities of such tasks is the utilization of Knowledge

Fig. 2. Application data as triples.

Graphs (KGs) that are capable of storing, processing, and querying linked data [17].

A. Internal Architecture

The Reasoning Framework relies on the open-source AllegroGraph⁵, a horizontally Distributed, multi-model (document and graph), entity-event knowledge graph technology that enables the extraction of sophisticated decision insights and predictive analytics from highly complex, distributed data that cannot be answered with conventional databases. Allegro-Graph provides an architecture through the REST protocol while there are Application Programmer's Interfaces (APIs) for various programming languages including Python [18]. This facilitates the enhancement of machine learning models,

²<https://kubernetes.io>

³<https://github.com/yannispolakis/HOCC>

⁴<https://openwhisk.apache.org>

⁵<https://allegrograph.com/products/allegrograph/>

Fig. 3. Resource data as triples.

which are typically served by Python-based applications, with features retrieved from the KB.

As shown in Fig 4, RF consists of a Flask-based backend service [19] that is responsible for exposing specific REST endpoints so that other platform components (i) ingest application and resource data, (ii) retrieve required information and (iii) inferred insights from the AllegroGraph for optimizing application design and deployment in terms of cost, latency, performance and more. Specifically, the design environment posts (see section III) the application graph to the Flask service that forwards it to the KB. In a similar way, utilizing the resource semantics component presented in [16], each cluster registered in the platform sends its description in the RF. Depending on the type of the input data, Flask guides AllegroGraph to create further relationships at both individual and default graph level. As further analyzed in the next subsection, this facilitates the timely retrieval of specific data needed by the platform as well as provides inference on the possible function allocations. The architecture follows the micro-services approach as both components (i.e., KG and

Flask) are containerized (using Docker⁶) and integrated as a single service allowing additional services to be added without affecting the existing component.

Fig. 4. Reasoning Framework's Architecture. The design environment and the registered clusters post application and resources data that forwarded to the AllegroGraph as individual graphs. Additional triples are either inserted or inferred via commands from the Flask to the KG. Platform components retrieve required data from dedicated REST endpoints offered by the Flask service.

B. Semantic Rules

After ingesting triples to the RF, these can be processed as graphs. With SPARQL queries to the KG, the required information, such as for example the workflows included in an application or the sizing of each cluster are made available as graph patterns [20]. However, some of these data require multiple queries to be retrieved and this results in increased processing time for the RF to respond to requests. For this purpose, specific relationships between the nodes of each input graph are implemented in the form of INSERT queries. Hence, all required information per provided endpoint can be instantly retrieved with a SELECT query. As an example, Fig 5 illustrates part of the available information of a target EKS cluster hosted in AWS before the INSERT query, where needed information (e.g. ram, cpu, architecture) for functions' allocations are part of each cluster node description. However, RF needs to aggregate such data to filter the clusters that do not meet application requirements. Such aggregations require multiple and complex queries as well transformations performed at the Flask service. On the other hand, after the INSERT operation (see Fig 6), performed during cluster registration in the platform, all the required data (e.g., cpu cores and ram) are available at cluster level and can be retrieved with a SELECT query.

Fig 7 illustrates an application consisting of an orchestrating flow that calls three other flows during deployment. Each of them has specific annotations, internal functions, and requirements. The target cluster should fulfill all this information for successful application deployment. Thus, application and resource matching could be cumbersome, especially for large workflows.

Although AllegroGraph's build-in reasoner automatically infers some types of relationships between the nodes of the ingested graphs, they do not suffice to assign connections between application and resource graph. To this end, several

⁶<https://www.docker.com>

Fig. 5. Resource Graph without INSERT queries. CPU cores and RAM size (in KB) are available only at cluster node level.

Fig. 6. Resource Graph after updating it with INSERT queries. Number of cluster nodes and CPU cores, and RAM size (in MB) are available and at cluster level. Cluster nodes are not displayed.

rules have been implemented to automate this process and create connections in the form of edges that link each flow with candidate target clusters. These rules enable RF to infer triples of the form `?flow :allocatable ?cluster` by comparing the requirements of the input application graph with the characteristics of the available resources. The latter allows retrieving all the information required to deploy an application with a simple SPARQL query that can be executed in a timely manner. Fig 8 depicts part of a deployment graph where the flows of the given application have been connected to the target

Fig. 7. Indicative Application Graph: An application consisting of a flow that calls three other flows as actions. Each flow has annotations such as execution mode, requirements (e.i., memory, timeout, locality) and includes functions that may also have annotations.

cluster, as indicated by the "Allocatable" edges of the graph.

Fig. 8. Deployment Graph: The edges "Allocatable" indicate the graph nodes of type "Flow" that could be hosted at the cluster with id "5653...72d".

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To illustrate the advantages and potential for further improvement of the proposed approach, this section focuses on analyzing the required response time per implemented endpoint for the two setups, called baseline and optimized. Their main difference is that the latter utilizes the semantic rules and reasoning presented in Section 4 which results in less complex queries and data manipulations in the Flask service.

Experiments are run on a desktop computer with an AMD Ryzen 5 5600x 6-Core CPU and 32GiB of RAM while the RF is deployed as a single service consisting of two Docker containers.

A. Reasoning Framework API endpoints

While application and resource matching is RF's primary task, it also provides specific data stored in its KB to other components in an asynchronous manner. Platform components responsible for the placement of the input application request data such as the built image location, parameters, and several annotations of each flow/function that are then used in typical Kubernetes and Openwhisk manifest files. Table I describes the REST endpoints currently used the most from the platform.

TABLE I
REASONING FRAMEWORK API DESCRIPTION

ID	Method	Endpoint ^a	Scope
EP1	POST	/cluster	Store a new cluster
EP2	GET	/cluster	Specs of stored clusters
EP3	POST	/app	Store a new app
EP4	GET	/app	Descriptions of all stored apps
EP5	GET	/app/run/a_id	Workflow allocations and manifest

^aOnly the most used endpoints are presented.

B. Reasoning Framework's Response Latency

Table II presents the mean response time per request for the most used endpoints of the RF. According to these experimental results, the optimized setup requires more time for storing the input resource and application data by 45.59%

and 15.57%, respectively. This is expected behavior since, during data ingestion, we perform additional operations to the AllegroGraph. On the other hand, query answering latency was significantly reduced for all the “GET” endpoints when utilizing KG’s capabilities.

It is noted that platform components will mainly call RF for requesting data (i.e., GET), while the posting of information happens in sparse intervals. For instance, cluster registration on the platform typically happens once and can be updated at some point in time if the cluster size is altered. On the other hand, requests for cluster specifications occur at each application deployment. Hence, the latency of the GET endpoints is of importance and can be further reduced by implementing additional rules in accordance with the requested data.

TABLE II
REASONING FRAMEWORK’S RESPONSE LATENCY

Endpoint ID	Required Time ^a (ms)		Relative Change (%)
	Baseline	Optimized	
EP1	68.99	100.45	45.59
EP2	28.32	6.58	-76.76
EP3	155.06	179.20	15.57
EP4	26.81	21.74	-18.91
EP5	166.42	110.71	-33.48

^aMean time of 10 sequential API calls.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper addresses the issue of enhanced application deployment and resource selection in hybrid cloud environments, including a number of functional and non functional requirements of an application. Support for common computing models such as services and functions is provided from the modelling and reasoning part. Using KGs, semantic reasoning, and linked data can introduce an effective approach to sharing required information across the platform components. In this direction, building on top of relevant works, a reference architecture for handling and utilizing application and resources metadata was presented, while a real-world implementation of this architecture was displayed. The proposed framework facilitates metadata storage, retrieval, and semantic reasoning over the input data, while at the same time, its RESTfull architecture permits the incorporation of additional analytical services.

Future work will focus on improving the efficiency of the proposed approach in terms of response time by including more semantic rules that will minimize query complexity. Moreover, new endpoints will be developed to utilize performance data from the infrastructure, such as the number of invocations and run-time per deployed function. The latter will enable to estimate deployment cost, identify bottlenecks of the given workflow, and push notifications and recommendations to the user for optimizing the developed workflows.

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